

LEVERAGING AI FOR ENHANCED APPLICATION SERVICE MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

When troubleshooting performance difficulties with distributed service-based cloud systems, it is essential to monitor their components and comprehend how they interact with one another. On the other hand, a lot of the current cloud monitoring solutions either don't work fully or need complex application and/or platform instrumentation, which makes them impossible to install on demand. Monitoring usually comes with a hefty price tag. This study presents the architecture of a cloud-based intelligent monitoring service network that can identify specific locations depending on predefined scenarios. Through a cloud server, our solution combines many CNNs that have been trained. These convolutional neural networks (CNNs) can recognize various features from webcam broadcasts. Figure 1 shows the three main components of our system: cameras, a cloud server for CNNs, and mobile terminals. In order to get the frames from the distant scene in real time, we employ a single webcam. We transmit these frames to our server in the cloud. In order to train CNN models, our cloud servers gather datasets from users. The findings of the recognition monitor are sent to the users' mobile terminals via the cloud server. Users may save a lot of computer resources by sharing trained models for comparable monitor applications. A hybrid CNN cloud server runs our whole monitoring system. In addition, we can optimize the number of virtual machines (VMs), physical locations of virtual machines (PMs), and servers (among other things) using artificial bee colony optimization. In comparison to current tools, our suggested model has much lower overhead, which results in a reduction of the monitoring-induced effect on reaction time of up to 89% and a reduction of resource consumption, including CPU and memory utilization, of up to 75%. An additional benefit is that the suggested deep learning module outperforms rival models in service identification by as much as 11%.

Keywords: Cloud Computing, Application Service Monitoring, Artificial Intelligence, Intelligent Monitor System, Convolutional Neural Network

Cite this Article: Hemanth Swamy, Leveraging AI For Enhanced Application Service Monitoring, *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(4), 2024, pp. 85-99.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_4/IJCET_15_04_006.pdf

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the rapid development of ICT, new types of urban areas known as "smart cities" are springing up. Smart technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), the blockchain, and fog computing have had a significant influence on these accomplishments [1]. Artificial intelligence (AI) has several potential uses in various fields, and one of them is healthcare. Other areas where AI has shown promise include pavement distress detection, pothole identification, and healthcare. Drones and other modern technologies are needed to monitor the detection of road and pavement deterioration and the distribution of medical and healthcare services. A lot of people are worried about the state of healthcare services and building sites. Increasingly, computer vision approaches are being applied to construction sites via the use of images and videos. [2]. The goal is to study how a gas station's customer service may be improved with the use of an Internet of Things (IoT) and artificial intelligence (AI) solution—specifically, a CCTV-based solution. An Internet of Things (IoT) and artificial intelligence (AI) solution built on CCTV helps with the implementation of service protocols, the collection of customer information, and safety assurance. A method that makes use of technology to assure the supply of services, enhance their experience, and guarantee their satisfaction. [3]. Care for prevalent chronic diseases that cause a lot of illness and death might be greatly improved with the use of AI, particularly predictive analytics. Nevertheless, accomplishing this goal remains fraught with several obstacles [4]. You can't escape the odd and unavoidable parts of reusability software in years of hatred. An architectural concept for organizing and using distributed features that may be managed by several domains is service-oriented architecture. Application components in this design model communicate with one another using network protocols to offer services to other elements in the application. Reusable handling project teams in software components often have extensive experience working with source code databases, allowing them to quickly locate and insert the necessary code into the program [5]. Recent years have seen tremendous progress in the use of AI in both the service and industrial sectors. The use of NLP (natural language processing) to improve user experience, efficiency, and human-machine interactions is one notable component [6]. There has been a lot of progress in generative artificial intelligence models, which have several uses, such as intelligent networks and AIGC services for mobile devices. Even though these models have a lot of promise, they also open the door to new security risks [7].

Fig.1. Data Services and Applications in Cloud

The complexity of industrial system monitoring and diagnostics is growing in tandem with the amount of data gathered and the number of tools and analytics that can connect data and events. Choosing the best data set for model training necessitates investment of time and expertise, and the implementation as well as training of these techniques and analytics are influencing factors in the best solution to deliver reliable and successful service [8].

Because it has such a direct bearing on people's health and welfare, research into RPMS is highly esteemed. Since the pandemic began, there has been an upsurge in the number of cases treated with RPMS. Despite their increasing usage, there are still obstacles to overcome, including accessibility, heterogeneous networks, automation, and QoS [9]. In order to address the increasing need for economical, efficient, and real-time healthcare services, smart city healthcare has lately profited substantially from the incorporation of AI technology. Artificial intelligence (AI) has demonstrated significant potential in many areas, including patient monitoring. The development of AI-based tracking devices has allowed for better health outcomes by allowing for continuous and tailored patient monitoring [10]. A promising new direction for smart city development is the merging of three popular technological trends: the IoT, AI, and blockchain technology. This will allow for more efficient monitoring and security of smart city infrastructure. One of the most significant technical revolutions since the merger of computers with transaction processing systems is currently taking place, and it is having a favorable effect: blockchain, AI, and the IoT [11]. Enhancing the security of financial services may be achieved via the revolutionary combination of AI and blockchain technology. By combining the best features of AI with blockchain, this integration strengthens confidence in banking transactions by reducing the likelihood of fraud, data breaches, and identity theft [12]. The complex and expensive nature of the IoT technologies for sensors is a barrier to implementing intelligent surveillance systems for agricultural machinery (AM). It might be difficult for remote places without network access to meet the demands of cloud and fog computing, which heavily rely on the accessibility of network infrastructure and specialist knowledge. As of yet, no commercially viable solution has made full use of edge devices, like cellphones, which have substantial processing capability [13]. The great biodiversity and many ecological services provided by grasslands have earned them a reputation as important habitats. A major hurdle to large-scale grassland surveillance is the difficulty of automating the recognition of indicator plants. These difficulties are caused by a lack of large datasets, changes in the distribution of datasets that are particular to grasslands and general datasets, and the fact that deep learning models are inherently opaque [14]. Hospitals, retirement homes, and assisted living facilities are in high demand due to the growing number of elderly people in the community. Through the use of intelligent technology, older people may lead fulfilling, self-sufficient lives within their communities, all while feeling safe and protected. Care for the elderly is one area where robots powered by AI are finding widespread application [15].

Evaluating, keeping tabs on, and managing infrastructure, applications, and services hosted in the cloud is what's known as cloud monitoring. Continuous addition and removal of services and components characterizes cloud systems. Applications that rely on monitoring in these ever-changing settings have strong backing from this research. The particular infrastructure and applications dictate which cloud services must be monitored. But, in general, the rules that follow:

- **Monitor all critical services:** Web servers, database servers, and application servers are all part of this category of services. Additionally, we need to keep an eye on any services that are crucial to the company's operations, such as the ERP or customer relationship management systems.
- **Monitor services that are experiencing problems:** We need to keep a careful eye on any service that is giving us trouble, like a lot of errors or a delayed response time, so we can figure out what's causing it.
- **Monitor services that are changing:** To make sure the changes we make to the cloud—like adding new apps or expanding the infrastructure—have the expected impact, we need to keep a careful eye on those services.

Some of the cloud applications that can need our attention are these.

Benefits of Cloud Monitoring

Any company, no matter how big or little, may reap the benefits of cloud monitoring. Here are a few of the main advantages:

- **Improved performance:** Significant gains in performance and reliability may be achieved via the use of cloud monitoring to detect and resolve performance issues with cloud-based applications and infrastructure.
- **Reduced costs:** By keeping tabs on your cloud resources, you may find and remove any unnecessary expenditure. Cloud monitoring can help us find underutilized virtual machines along with storage volumes, so we can eliminate them.
- **Increased security:** You can react faster to security risks with the aid of cloud monitoring. One use case is the detection of harmful activity on your cloud databases and servers via the use of cloud monitoring.
- **Improved compliance:** Industry standards such as HIPAA as well as PCI DSS may be better met with the use of cloud monitoring. Organizations must keep an eye on their IT systems in order to identify and counteract security risks, as mandated by these rules.
- **Better business insights:** The efficiency of cloud-based apps and infrastructure may be better understood with the help of cloud monitoring. With this data, we can enhance our decision-making and fine-tune our cloud infrastructure.

For businesses to get the most out of cloud computing with the least amount of hassle, tracking clouds is a must-have tool.

RELATED WORK

The authors suggested a cloud-based solution to pool ANN computing resources in order to cut down on unnecessary computation in [12]. To provide intelligent monitoring services, they offer a cloud-based intelligent monitoring system in that article. Hybrid convolutional neural networks were used in the system's creation. Multiple intelligent monitor tasks have made use of it, including detecting scene changes, recognizing strangers, recognizing facial expressions, and recognizing actions. Within the framework of smart cities, that research seeks to investigate the effects and possibilities of such advances on healthcare services [13]. Fog computing offers an interesting alternative to integrated cloud computing for Internet of Things applications by bringing processing near to the network's edge devices. With fog computing, data may be processed and stored closer to its source rather than in the cloud, which reduces latency, increases security, and speeds up operations. By bridging the gap between Internet of Things (IoT) sensors and devices and cloud data centers, fog computing enhances service management and resource allocation. Connectivity between devices, distributed ledgers, and fog computing substantially enhance healthcare in smart cities. Problems with security of information, interoperability, and cost effectiveness continue to arise in healthcare systems that use IoT. Blockchain technology, on the other hand, may be useful for facilitating data interchange, establishing decentralized databases, and safeguarding private information. Examine how techniques and tools based on AI can improve the functioning of complex applications in order to support the diverse infrastructure layer in the "computing continuum" [14] by enhancing IaC optimization, IaC self-learning, and IaC self-healing. Thus, the current study suggests a suite of tools, procedures, and techniques that application operators can use to: optimize application deployment as well as adaptation while optimizing execution; maximize the effectiveness of distributed application installation across different computing resources; keep a real-time eye on execution structures, like continuous control along with trust in infrastructure amenities; self-recover from attacks that cause unexpected errors; and optimize application deployment along with adaptation. Reference [15] details an experiment that ran from August 2020 to October 2020 at a Mumbai gas station.

The study is based on data gathered over a period of time. Conclusion: A CCTV-based system might be useful for identifying, recording, and accessing client movement and behavior on the gasoline station forecourt, according to their study. In addition, it works well for recording safe habits, which in turn make customers feel secure and happy. As a result, studies have shown that implementing IoT may improve customer experience and sales by improving customer identification, operational efficiency, and customer acquisition, retention, and satisfaction. First of its type, the research looks at how customer experience in Indian petrol retailing might be improved via the use of CCTV-based solutions. A digitized cultural heritage server that offers basic data support, knowledge aids, engineering applications, and visual exhibits using HTTP queries is suggested in the article [16]. That system incorporated a plethora of algorithms for analyzing data pertaining to cultural heritage. Consequently, that platform incorporates a system for managing cultural heritage data, a system for building and applying cultural heritage knowledge, a system for displaying, analyzing, and evaluating cultural assets, and a system for monitoring the cultural heritage microenvironment index. Furthermore, the platform offered an API for expert-level, tailored programming, allowing for efficient support. That platform is designed to be easily modified and expanded upon, providing a strong basis for the digital exchange of cultural heritage information. Deploying, automatically discovering services, monitoring, and adaptively evolving applications are all parts of the cloud service lifecycle that might benefit from patterns, according to [17]'s suggestion. That paper's central argument is that dynamic patterns may simplify the process of creating, releasing, and improving cross-cloud applications. While maintaining compatibility with the owner's personal computer, high-performance computing centers, cloud services, and distributed systems as a whole, the design in [18] takes a minimalistic approach. A Python interface, a command-line interface for accessing a REST service, and a graphical user interface for controlling and monitoring the workflow are all part of that framework's access. Like other deep learning systems, it makes use of a template-based batch administration system to generate repeatable experiments by generating permutations over chosen experiment parameters using configuration files. The resulting framework serves as a teaching tool for both academics and students, and it is purpose-built for analytics operations with the objective of achieving the MLCommons requirements for AI applications on hybrid computing platforms. Additionally, it is capable of doing calculations on platforms spanning from a single machine to thousands of machines, whether in the cloud or on-premises. As an example of the tool's value, they built an application accuracy guideline for the MLCommons Science Working Group's Cloudmask application that is based on FAIR. This open-source project may be found on GitHub and is based on Cloudmesh, an easily enhanced framework. It has a wide variety of possible uses. The advantages of service-oriented architecture in mobile medicine are usually first investigated by academics [19]. That paper expands upon previous work by the author on the topic of medical services platforms that use the SOC paradigm to orchestrate and compose web services from a shared cloud repository, thus allowing for the unification of application development for patients, doctors, and the central server. That method allows for the development of apps that are personalized to each patient based on his illness and home treatment regimen. Incorporating greater intelligence throughout the whole flow of incident management is crucial for cloud systems to allow them to provide more dependable online services and applications, according to [20]. That paper showcases a project that exemplifies how Microsoft is pursuing these aims using AIOps methods. The incident management process and the difficulties it faces in practice are first described. Next, we'll go into detail about the machine learning and artificial intelligence approaches that were used to address these difficulties. To show how intelligent and beneficial these techniques were for Microsoft service products, we'll provide some application outcomes.

The writers of [21] center their attention on the healthcare system's overall quality of service needs and the specific devices found at different stages of the innovative healthcare infrastructure. There are five main contributions to that paper. Primarily, it presents a novel approach to pre-SLR keyword research, which may be used to extract high-quality SLR from pertinent research articles. Second, smart healthcare applications' service quality is the main focus of the discussion of SLR. Thirdly, it discusses several methods that smart healthcare applications have utilized to improve service quality. As a fourth point, it takes a look at the key metrics used to evaluate smart healthcare applications nowadays. Finally, it offers answers to the questions raised by the challenges of providing high-quality service in intelligent healthcare IoT applications. In order to forecast AV traffic rates using multi-cloud services, the aforementioned study's authors suggest a deep learning strategy based on the bidirectional long-short-term memory (BI-LSTM) framework [22]. Regarding the accuracy of batch size forecasts, we contrast the BI-LSTM with the unidirectional LSTM. The authors analyze the processing period, mean absolute percentage of error, root mean square error, and coefficient of determination to ascertain the correctness of the predictions. When it comes to making accurate predictions, BI-LSTM is better than the LSTM model. Also, using 8 batch sizes to make predictions is very accurate compared to the competitors. In order to address such an issue with AI-based help aggregation, some industrial applications will use edge computing, as discussed earlier in the study [23]. With the help of Service Aggregation Edge, you may achieve reliability, high storage capacity, a long duty cycle, and energy efficiency. In [24], the authors suggest a healthcare system that uses chatbots and a database stored in the cloud. A chatbot-based mobile healthcare system is proposed as a means to provide quick care in the case of common accidents as well as adjustments in the situation of patients with long-term diseases. The public may easily have access to a range of health services using chatbots—intelligent conversation platforms that engage with users via a talking interface—thanks to the possibility of connecting through the top social networking messengers. The proposed design enables natural human-robot interaction, which will aid in the successful launch of the chatbot medical service. There are four main components that constitute the framework: data, information, knowledge, and service.

PROPOSED WORK

A. Research problems

The cloud framework demonstrated in Figure 3 provides consumers with a variety of services. A service request (SR) is the formal request that users make to access cloud computing services. A service request may presumably be divided out. This may be accomplished by looking at many real-life instances that rely heavily on data. For example, data from smart city CCTV systems, environmental air quality monitoring, apps that create massive amounts of data from Internet of Things devices, etc., may be partitioned and distributed across several cloud environments. Cloud computing, on the other hand, makes use of a huge pool of resources and is therefore better able to manage the resource demands of services. The next sections detail the user model, service demands, and the cloud environment's offerings, all while keeping this assumption and context in mind. The phrasing of the relevant issue follows this.

B. System Model

Modern times have seen the rapid expansion of cloud-based services. Web service development and use have been accelerated by the introduction of cloud computing. It works with more OSes and lessens the load on software virtual machines. It also improves infrastructure usage. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and other forms of artificial intelligence (AI) are paving the way for the smart monitoring systems that we use every day.

It takes a lot of energy and computational resources to complete even a basic operation with a single CNN. Since this is the case, we suggest a cloud-based method for CNN computation resource sharing in order to cut down on duplicate calculations. To provide intelligent monitoring services, we offer a cloud-based intelligent monitoring system in this article. Hybrid convolutional neural network networks were used in the system's creation.

Fig.2 Major Modules in Proposed Work

Fig.3. Proposed Work Flow Model

Assumptions: A variety of m-services were given by the local CN, F, who is represented by. Each service's representation is denoted by $S = \{s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_m\}$ where $0 < k \leq m$. Slicing user SRs and distributing them throughout the fog and cloud nodes is CN's principal role. Slices are logical representations of portions of service requests that are used to divide the incoming data. Take a 100-MB movie file as an example. It may be divided into four equal parts, each containing 25 MB of footage. Every CN service has a sensitivity rating that shows how important it is compared to the others. The sensitivity, denoted as s_k , of a service is $\bar{\rho}_k^s, 0 < \bar{\rho}_k^s \leq 1$. The CN supposedly decides how sensitive the services are. A greater value for $\bar{\rho}_k^s$ provide care that is gentler. A lower sensitivity setting is used by the service that processes user-uploaded videos compared to the one that processes CCTV footage.

C. Workload Prediction Model

Anybody having an internet connection may take advantage of CN's set of services. Suppose we include every user who is currently connected to the set. $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$. An approach to user identification is by u_i , where $0 < i \leq n$. A user may submit many types of service requests. An unsigned binary value returns the status of the service used by user u_i . statistically speaking,

$$u_i(s_k) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if user } u_i \text{ is availing the service of type } s_k \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Prioritization based on distance: When determining a user's position inside the maximum range of the CN, a certain distance is taken into account. Like the CN, every user has their own unique location parameter. Following these steps, By using the conventional geometric formula, one may ascertain the user's distance,

$$d_i = \sqrt{(p_i - p)^2 + (q_i - q)^2} \quad (2)$$

where (p_i, q_i) is the precise coordinates of the nearby CN, where u_i is placed, and (p, q) . The user's distance is obviously less than the fog node's maximum range, D . In order to calculate the distance-based priority, we consider the user's distance (d_i) with the maximum range (D),

$$\wp_i^d = \frac{d_i}{D}, \forall u_i \in D \quad (3)$$

All users within a certain radius will be given equal weight, depending on their proximity. The users with the farthest distances will get the most consideration.

Rank according to latency: A latency-based precedence is implemented, comparable to the distance-based importance, with the assumption that users closer to the CN may not necessarily have lower latency. Let, ζ_i being the user's round-trip delay (RTD). The latency-based priority may be determined using this number,

$$\wp_i^\zeta = \frac{\zeta_i}{\max\{\zeta_j | 0 < j \leq n\}} \quad (4)$$

$\wp_i^\zeta$ is subjective and relies on the aggregated latency data from all users online. A higher percentage of our customers are given maximum priority.

User Priority: The overall user priority may be calculated using the following formula, which takes into consideration the distance-based choice in Equation 5 and the latency-based choice in Equation 4.

$$\wp_i = \wp_i^d + \wp_i^\zeta \quad (5)$$

A SR from a user is sliced into $\tilde{s}_i^k$ total SRs. A value larger than zero is required for an SR's number of slices $\tilde{s}_i^k = 0$, stands for the fact that the customer isn't using the offering. The worth $\tilde{s}_i^k = 1$ indicates that the CN will be the only one to handle the service request since it is not being sliced.

The resource need that corresponds to each SR is denoted by $u_i(R_k^x)$. There are two distinct types of demand for resources: $x = \{CPU, MEM\}$. The total demand for resources may be determined by adding up the demands for both the minimal or base resources and the auxiliary resources.

The extra demand for resources caused by input data sizes that might vary is known as auxiliary resource demand. Let, $u_i(\bar{R}_k^x)$ to the user's basic resource demand for the s_k kind SR u_i . Similarly, let $u_i(\bar{R}_k^x)$, the kind of SR's auxiliary resource requirement s_k from the user u_i . When we add up the demands for both primary and secondary resources, we get the overall demand for resources as,

$$u_i(R_k^x) = u_i(\bar{R}_k^x) + u_i(\bar{R}_k^x) \tag{6}$$

In addition, it is necessary to determine the resource consumption for each slice while slicing the SR. Each SR slice's total resource demand is the sum of the basic resource demand and the auxiliary resource need, divided by the total number of slices. From a mathematical perspective,

$$u_i(R_{k,j}^x) = u_i(\bar{R}_k^x) + \frac{u_i(\bar{R}_k^x)}{\bar{s}_i^k} \tag{7}$$

An additional identifier for each SR is its size. An SR's size, often called the input data size, is a measure of the SR's overall size. Let, $u_i(\bar{s}_k)$ be the extent to which user u_i has an SR of type s_k . It is possible to determine the SR slice size using this information.

$$u_i(\bar{s}_{k,j}) = \frac{u_i(\bar{s}_k)}{\bar{s}_i^k} \tag{8}$$

Every slice in a given SR has the same size, meaning. $u_i(\bar{s}_{k,j_1}) = u_i(\bar{s}_{k,j_2}), j_1 \neq j_2, 0 < j_1, j_2 < \bar{s}_i^k, \forall u_i \in U$. One SR slice will be smaller than the other since SRs vary in size.. Hence, $u_{i_1}(\bar{s}_{k,j}) = u_{i_2}(\bar{s}_{k,j}), \forall u_{i_1}, u_{i_2} \in U, i_1 \neq i_2$.

The service demand, indicated as SD (s_k), represents the total amount of service that all connected individuals at CN F are requesting. This may be determined by adding up all the SR sizes from all users and adding up the overall number of service users. From a mathematical perspective,

$$SD(s_k) = \sum_{\forall u_i \in U} [u_i(\bar{s}_k) * u_i(s_k)] \tag{9}$$

where $u_i(s_k)$ is a variable that denotes if the user is using the service bk and $u_i(\bar{s}_k)$ stands for the magnitude of the user's s_k service requests size u_i .

Service Relevancy and Criticality: Information on the relationships between monitoring data (such as data consistency, service reliance, or temporal causality) is crucial for finding associations within the monitoring data. One typical data relationship in the cloud is data dependence. When it comes to providing OpenSSL encryption on connections between cloud servers and service consumers, a certain version of the cryptography library (i.e., "1.0.1," omitting "1.0.1g") is known to be dependent on data. Consequently, data relations make it easier to find data correlations. The properties of the monitoring data are just as important as the data relationship when it comes to finding data correlations. Our focus in this dissertation is on two characteristics of monitoring data. The goal of capturing the requirement of acquired monitoring data is data reducibility, a characteristic. For example, because the "pcscd" daemon is used to do Dropbox's directory scan, which involves reading and accessing many files in subdirectories repeatedly, it produces a great deal of repetitive monitoring data. The data collected by repeated monitoring does not provide any valuable insights. Therefore, data reducibility should be appropriately used to eliminate the worthless (repetitive) data. Data criticality, which aims to capture the relevance of the monitoring data, is another feature.

If we were to monitor the aforementioned ADCA assault, for example, we would care more about data showing the success or failure of cache access than about data showing the success or failure of file access. As a result, the use of data criticality should be prioritized while managing monitoring data.

Service priority: When distributing resources to service slices, service priority indicates how important each service is. Distinct from service sensitivity, this one takes into account factors like relative service demand, latency, and the distance and number of users connected. Service priority of type s_k , represented by $\wp_k^s$, can be calculated as follows,

$$\wp_k^s = \omega_1 * \sum_{\forall u_i \in U} [\wp_i * u_i(\bar{s}_k)] + \omega_2 * \frac{SD(s_k)}{\sum_{\forall s_j \in S} SD(s_j)} \quad (10)$$

The constant parameters ω_1 and ω_2 are used to influence the relative weight of certain factors. On the other hand, the constant values must be within the bounds of $\omega_1 + \omega_2 = 1$. Two terms make up Equation 10. For the first term, we add up the number of service requests with the total priority of every user, s_k . The user's connection latency and distance from the closest fog node are the determining factors in their priority. The third component represents the relative service demand and is determined by dividing the total service demand received by the fog node by the ratio of demand for present service requests.

Fig.4. Workflow Prediction Model D. Cloud Application Service Monitoring

It is the responsibility of the monitoring engine to gather the necessary monitoring data in accordance with the items listed in the tracking templates. The monitoring repository is where all of this data is saved. The monitoring coordinator and tracking agents using the ABC algorithm are the two main parts of the monitoring engine.

Data supplied by monitoring agents is aggregated and stored by the monitoring coordinator. The coordinator maintains tabs on the agents that are actively monitoring. By communicating necessary metrics to agents placed on target hosts, it delegated monitoring chores. Once the coordinator has finished collecting data, they will put it in a tracking repository.

Developers may use our cloud system's APIs to control many aspects of it. Data collection APIs, intelligent monitor APIs, configuration APIs, and authentication APIs are all part of it. To validate logins, authentication APIs are used. Users may configure their personal information, including webcam addresses and informed terminals, using configuration APIs. Our intelligent monitoring cloud server provides a number of monitoring services, and authorized customers may access these services using our APIs. It updates preconfigured terminals with the latest monitor findings and continually uploads image data from cameras. In order to import their training datasets, users make use of data collection APIs.

A request is added to the appropriate queue by the cloud server as soon as it arrives. The four distinct kinds of task queues are processed by the server when the scheduler is executed. It discovers idle computing nodes and assigns them jobs by popping them. Prediction tasks for monitoring systems often need processing in real time. This means that jobs involving prediction are more important. In this particular setup, prediction jobs take up half of the computing nodes. The training of algorithms utilizes 40% of the compute nodes. In order to gather training data, 5% of compute nodes are used. Parallel processing using GPUs is unnecessary in these data-gathering nodes. Nevertheless, a lightning-fast storage system and network are necessities. To handle simple user queries, the remaining 5% of computing nodes are put to use. There are exceptions to the assignment approach. Actually, as new computing nodes become available, the cloud servers will allocate more of them to training jobs. Fig. 6 depicts the analysis of monitoring overhead.

Fig.6. Monitoring Overhead Analysis

Fig.7. Response Time Analysis vs. No of VMs

Fig.8. Service Execution Success Rate (%)

Figs. 7 and 8 illustrate the performance of the response time and service execution success rate for the proposed work based on with and without monitoring.

CONCLUSION

The significance of an intelligence monitoring network is expected to grow in the near future. The evolution of cloud-based services is rapid. Intelligence monitoring systems that rely on the cloud will soon be available. A growing number of tasks will be handled by systems like this. Cloud computing and machine learning, two of computer science's most talked-about topics, have come a long way in the last decade. Our findings demonstrate the practicality of developing such a monitoring system. We started by planning the specifics of a monitoring system's architecture. Integrating these two technologies paves the way for next-gen cloud computing. Things like real-time performance, security, and resource consumption still need to be taken care of in order to build a fully-fledged cloud-based monitoring system. Further investigation is required to determine the impact of cluster node count, data transfer rate, and job execution time. We should also improve the services offered by this kind of technology. Indeed, for reasons like ethnic variation and individual differences, massive quantities of training data are required to build a universal deep algorithm for human face expression detection. Therefore, in order to progressively enhance the recognition applications, the system is continuously gathering data from various users.

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Citation: Hemanth Swamy, Leveraging AI For Enhanced Application Service Monitoring, *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(4), 2024, pp. 85-99

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